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Protests in Latin America in the middle of ongoing global systemic crises¹

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Abstract

The last years have observed a series of mounting challenges that have deepened tensions in the region, as illustrated by the increase in the number of protests in the region. The increase in tensions relate to the intersection of worsening of living conditions for millions of citizens- a consequence of the pandemic, the ripple effects of Russian aggression towards Ukraine, and the concerns about a coming global recession. These tensions will bring challenges to political systems across the region, manifested in the occurrence of different types of protests, and the risk of declining support for democracy in Latin America, should governments fail to respond to the demands of their citizens.

Keywords: Inequalities, protest, Latin America, democracy, collective action.

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1. The continuation of mobilisations in the region

The first decade of the 21st century, was described around a narrative of economic growth for Latin America, the second decade was one of economic stagnation, and the current decade seems to be one of uncertainty and apprehension.

This as, according to World Bank data, between 2000 and 2019, the region's annual growth was "on average 1.6%, [... lower than other] regions such as East Asia (4.8%), Europe, Central Asia (1.9%), the Middle East (2.9%), South Asia (6.5%) and Sub-Saharan Africa (3.5%)" (López, 2020).

This "moderate economic growth, limits the economic opportunities [...] for the population" (López, 2020). As Latin America has followed mostly an "enclave model" of development, "development" has benefited some, and excluded most of the population of the region from reaping the benefits of economic growth (Bértola, L., & Ocampo, J. A.; 2012).

Table 1. Number of protests in Latin America and the Caribbean between 2019 and 2022

Year	Protest	Violence against civilians
2019	12 535	6 010
2020	14 697	6 500
2021	19 206	7 209
2022	19 471	8 811

Source: [ACLED](#)

The increase in tensions in recent years is evinced by "social explosions" and ongoing tensions taking place across the region (See Table 1). Peru, Bolivia, Colombia, and Chile, illustrate how mobilisations respond to the absence of meaningful reforms directed at the improvement in the wellbeing of citizens across the region, and persistent inequalities, poverty, and precariousness.

These conditions speak of the exclusion to which citizens are subjected to, and the challenge of making opportunities and rewards attainable for citizens across the region. Then, it should be no surprise to observe the emergence of demands from historically marginalised groups that seek to achieve change via different political vehicles, including mobilisation and protests. The salience of mobilisations by indigenous, afro-descendent and women's rights groups in the region, should be not seen as a surprise, and rather as a natural outcome to the current state of affairs.

Protests have aimed to place pressure on governments, political parties, and institutions. They are a vehicle to give a voice to the demands and interests of different sectors in society. Protests also have been used by contending parties to leverage their demands. The ability to build and organize collective action in the region has been facilitated by the growing legitimacy of protests as legitimate vehicles across different ends of the political spectre. This explains the presence of protests from the political

left and the right as a common feature across the region. This is the case even in countries where protests used to be stigmatized, as in Colombia (Díaz Pabón, 2020).

The persistence of protests not only illustrates the challenge of legitimacy but also the unwillingness of elites to respond to social demands (Lissardy, 2019). The growth of protests relates also to unresolved societal demands within different forms of democratic and less democratic regimes and the incapacity of state institutions to fulfil past agreements. The prevalence of protests should be understood not only in a national, regional, but also in a transnational key, as movements are displaying transnational solidarities across the region (i.e., indigenous groups expressing solidarities across the region).

Two broad types of protests have emerged in the region. Firstly, protests associated with socio economic development demands, such as the access and provision of public services, socio economic rights, and environmental rights. Secondly, there is the continuation of the mobilization from historically marginalized groups, and their protests in relation to old grievances and new societal demands (such as the inclusion of rights for LGBTIQ+ groups, and post-colonial demands). These two types of mobilizations interact with ongoing institutional crises, external shocks, and the discontent with elites in power and their (perceived or real) lack of response to citizens' demands.

An example of the first type, are the 2019 protests in Chile over inequality, Ecuador over the elimination of fuel subsidies, Haiti over shortages of gasoline and food, or the protests in Colombia between 2019 and 2021.

An example of the second type, relates to demands about the defence of marginalized nations (indigenous and Afro- descendant groups), the mobilizations by different feminist movements, and the defence of animal rights. Mobilizations defending these agendas have been active and managed to articulate themselves to nation-wide cycles of protest and collective action, aiming to draw the attention and support of society to their demands.

Protests in the 21st century are characterized by a population with greater access to education and information tools, which allow them to create and contest more easily existing narratives. Education, social media, and information facilitates the emergence of mobilizations that demand the fulfilment of the obligations of the state. Latin America observes important segments of the population willing to fight for their right to afford a livelihood and for protecting and expanding their rights. This explains not only the bulging demands to states for fulfilling their duties, but also the coordination, sophistication of protesting organizations as well as the emergence of new idioms of protests (for example the “*el violador eres tú*” denunciation performance).

To reflect on the emergence of these protests, we proceed to discuss the rearing systemic crisis and their shocks on livelihoods, then we consider the international tensions due to the beginning of a new

cold war, and finally we reflect on how these developments can influence protests and tensions in the region.

2. The rearing of a systemic crisis

According to the latest report of Global Protest Tracker (2023), there is an increase in anti-government protests throughout the world. Not only protests have increased, but the tendency of governments to respond to societal demands in an authoritarian way has increased as "[...] unnecessary and/or excessive force against protesters [has been reported] in at least 85 of the 154 countries studied in 2022" (Amnesty International, 2023).

Mobilization has been on the rise despite the use of violence and repression from different states against protestors (i.e., Peru, Venezuela, Bolivia, Nicaragua, Chile), the incorporation of societal demands through reforms of varying intensity (i.e. Ecuador), or the prospects of change by the arrival of governments that seem to be aligned with the demands of some of the mobilising organizations (i.e., Colombia, Argentina, or Brazil) (see Table 1).

Given the weak prospect of inclusion of protestors' demands in meaningful reforms, the increasing repression, the uncertainty generated by the inability of governments to fully resolve historical demands for representation and inclusion, and the growing tensions over the livelihoods of millions of people on the continent, these forces put governance at risk, as "governments cannot simultaneously maintain legitimacy and [fail to] promote socio-economic development" (Alcántara, 2009, pp 12).

The weakening of legitimacy is illustrated by the emergence of "*Primera Línea*" organizations across different protests. These are collectives of demonstrators who aim to protect protestors from police abuse, using shields, laser pointers or homegrown means to counteract the tools used by police forces against protestors, and whose mission is to protect protestors and confront police forces. Also, the attempts at counter institutional efforts as illustrated by the attempt at overthrowing elected officers and institutions as in Brazil in January 2023, are an illustration of the weakening of the legitimacy of state institutions at different levels.

This wearing of legitimacy is taking place at both sides of the political spectrum. While state legitimacy is not solely defined by the legitimacy of police forces, or the respect to electoral results, the fact that some civilians are opting to take over the mission of police forces with regards of the protection of civilians or trying to trigger coups in the face of unexpected electoral results, is telling.

We argue that this erosion of legitimacy relates to the frameworks that connect institutions and citizens, and their weakening. As the Barometer of the Americas 2021 reports, levels of support for democracy and the satisfaction with democracy are lower than in the past decade in Latin America.

These intersecting trends are compounded in Latin America by how the socio-economic conditions of a significant share of the population have worsened after the pandemic as "201 million people (32.1% of the total population of the region) live in poverty, of which 82 million (13.1%) are in extreme poverty" (CEPAL, 2022, pp. 12).

While the legacy of pandemic was one of sending millions of people to poverty, this shock has in fact deepened as inflationary pressures due to the supply chain disruptions during the pandemic, the impact of the Russian aggression to Ukraine, and growing speculation in food prices by large conglomerates, which are being aggravated by the decisions from the Federal Reserve of the USA by raising interest rates. Increasing interest rates will lead to "persistent inflationary pressures affecting the economies of the region" (World Bank, 2022), and will affect the wellbeing of citizens in the region, as the servicing of international debts will consume the already spare resources allocated to social protection.

It should not be thus surprising to observe protests throughout the region centring their critiques around the economic model, the political systems, and their responsibility pushing people to poverty and precariousness in urban and rural areas.

This is evidenced in mobilizations from "peripheral" areas towards capital cities, as in Chile, Peru, Bolivia, Ecuador, and Colombia. In Latin America "more than 123 million people live in rural areas, [with] poverty rates [of] 45.7% and extreme poverty [rates of] 21.7 %" (ILO, 2020). Thus, these mobilizations are an example of the response of citizens towards states that seem to procrastinate on the responses to their previous demands.

Whereas mobilizations from different groups have achieved national and regional visibility thanks to their efforts and coordination, it is yet to be seen if the responses from different governments will lead to reforms that can effectively respond to the demands of those taking the streets.

The occurrence of protests does not necessarily mean less support for democracy, but the repressive response of states and their anomie has not helped either. Since 2019, some protests have been tinged by violence from either protest movements or states, which have led to a reduction in the governance across the region. Most governments in the region still read dissent as a risk to authority and respond to protests via repression.

This forgets that such vision of governance resembles more an authoritarian mode of government than a democratic one. A point in case is the case of Peru, in which the tensions following the ousting of Castillo after his attempt at a self-coup were preceded by four different presidents in a period of less than two years. As the case of Peru illustrates, repression against civilians have preceded the escalation of different demands and the erosion of the legitimacy of state institutions.

For Latin America, this crisis can be explained by the pre-existing fragility of democracy, related to the long transition processes away from USA-sponsored dictatorships, high inequalities, and the recurrence of discourses that present authoritarian means as better (take for example the discourses of Bolsonaro

in Brazil), evidenced in the emergence of populist politicians promising more results for the “people” with a system of governance with less restrictions on what they can do and what they cannot do.

According to V-dem "the level of democracy enjoyed by the average global citizen is at 1986 levels, and for Latin America, – eight countries – are generating processes of democratic regression Brazil, Chile, El Salvador, Guatemala, Haiti, Peru, Nicaragua, Uruguay and Venezuela" (V-dem, 2023, pp. 11), this is presenting a concerning development as could indicate a slide to less democratic forms of governments (Mainwaring & Pérez Liñán, 2023, pp. 158).

Not only the promise and the expectation of change will be fundamental in informing future protests. As ongoing and coming shocks of current and future wars, climate change, and increase in interest rates will affect the poorest and more vulnerable in the region. Hence, in countries led by indifferent elites, this will naturally lead to anger and justified resentment regarding an absence of justice for the majority of the population in the face of a series of privileges and prerogative for the elites (Shifter, 2020).

Should this occur, citizens will deepen their challenges to the structures of different countries, their fictions, narratives, and the way in which they create, justify, and reproduce existing social orders. In the face of unsympathetic elites, greater instability and even violence, and support advocates of less democratic means of governance that can provide what “democracy” has not -the legitimate claims for the right to afford a livelihood will be more likely.

3. Polycrisis, a new cold war, and the enabling of authoritarian populisms.

In this precarious and unstable scenario, the Russian aggression to Ukraine and the expanding economic, political and diplomatic presence of aspiring hegemons such as China and Russia and their influence on governments in the region (i.e., Venezuela, Nicaragua, Cuba, Argentina), will deepen geopolitical tensions in Latin-America, and seem to point that the region- like the world might be approaching a "polycrisis" (Tooze, 2022).

The feature of such type of crisis is the difficulty of changing the inertial forces that seem to continue driving different regions towards further instability in which “shocks are disparate, but they interact [and feedback on each other making the aggregate impact worse]” (Tooze, 2022). Such prospect has led to some authors to state that such crisis is unavoidable as “a holistic and global response would be required, which the [current] system itself would not be able to generate” (Morin and Kern, 1999, pp 74).

This crisis is driven by internal and external factors, in which the tensions of a rearing new cold war³ will exacerbate tensions, as different international actors will support competing internal actors, as they

³ The Cold War was a period of geopolitical tension between the United States and the Soviet Union that spanned from the end of the second world war until the collapse of the Soviet Union. The term cold war is used because

instrumentalize internal tensions for their goals in the middle of a global competition for control and influence over technology, natural resources and political influence across the globe.

The growing influence of international actors in the region is illustrated by the refusal of Mexico's President to impose sanctions against Russia, the hesitancy by the Brazilian government to denounce the invasion of Ukraine, or the reception in Venezuela of a high-level delegation from the USA, shortly after the invasion of Ukraine. This illustrates the existence of a global market for political and economic support, which potentially can enable greater autonomy and sovereignty, but also can enable greater leverage for less democratic regimes (Beech Dahi & López 2022).

The combination of the pandemic, different and compounding economic crises, international and domestic fragility, and entrenched inequalities, represent a complex, volatile, and difficult panorama, which increases and deepens the tension in the relations between citizenship and states, as it seems the current events seem to have overwhelmed the capacity (or interest) of institutions to respond to societal demands across the region and explains why democracy in the region less appealing.

This fatigue with the current working of states has been manifested "into broad levels of citizen fatigue, [...] social protests, and electoral [outcomes], which end up rejecting traditional political parties and elites" (Sanahuja, 2022, pp 108). Such fatigue relates to the discontent with democracy as a model of governance and the growing support for models of "benevolent" authoritarianism.

This weariness with democracy, explains the re-emergence of opportunist politicians from the right and left, and their election based on discourses in which internal and external enemies are created, with narratives that are contemptuous about democracy, and risk deinstitutionalizing states.

These styles of government have been manifested in the challenges to existing institutional frameworks, with the promise of "getting things done in the name of the people" and has been evinced by the election of Jair Bolsonaro in Brazil, the attempted coup following the election of Lula da Silva in 2022, the election of Andrés Manuel López Obrador in Mexico in 2018, or the risk of militarization of states as in El Salvador touted by Bukele.

These leaders claim their "direct" communication with their voting bases as central to their style of politics, and their source of legitimacy, in which populism is a vehicle to bypass traditional parties and institutions (Mudde and Rovira, 2017). Populism as a style of politics, is nor proprietorial from the right, as history shows how this also allowed the consolidation of a wave of left-wing governments between 1998-2015 (Rafael Correa, Lula Da Silva, Cristina Kirchner, Hugo Chavez, and Evo Morales). Yet, while this wave of left-leaning populist governments has ended, the use of populism and the pressures over

illustrating the absence of large-scale fighting directly between the two superpowers, but their clash via opposing sides in different regional conflicts. As the events in Syria, Yemen, Iraq, and Ukraine illustrate a new wave of conflicts in which existing and aspiring hegemony clash in their quest for influence and power.

institutions and democracy by charismatic individuals in power has not stopped as the arrival of new left wing and right-wing politicians such as Bolsonaro, Bukele, or Ortega who promise to fight against poverty, inequality, corruption, and violence.

The continuity of populism and their success as appealing to the voice of the unheard, resonates with the occurrence of past and current protests against governments in the region (i.e., protests against Castillo in Peru- before his ousting, and Petro in Colombia). The continuity of crises of governability, has informed the use of mobilization as a way of doing politics by other means by opposition parties and ruling governments. Because of this, less democratic parties now complement their repertoires with calls to mobilize and use protest (against or in support of) as a form of political action.

This scenario can be the gateway (or the return) to fascism and other forms of authoritarian models of government. The possibility of appealing to popular discourses and the attempts at de-institutionalizing democracies, has been illustrated by the emergence of right-wing parties which have gained traction in the region. This, however, is not a monopoly of right-wing parties, as in the case of Nicaragua and Venezuela, left wing discourses have been accompanied by a reduction of political rights and in some cases a de-facto cessation of rights. Take for example, Venezuela where the effective cessation of basic public services explains extremely high maternal death rates, and lower life expectancy than before 2010.

In Latin America, the past presidency of Bolsonaro in Brazil, the popularity of Bukele in El Salvador, the candidacy of José Antonio Kast for the Chilean presidential elections of 2021, and the continuity of Ortega and Maduro in Nicaragua and Venezuela, show that populism aligned with nationalist discourses that wield the reduction of rights can be successfully mobilized making use of internal tensions and international support for enabling the arrival of, or support less democratic models of statehood. All these governments share "three characteristics: nativism, authoritarianism and populism" (Mudde, 2019).

The return of Trump into electoral politics in the USA, will enable the justification of less institutional forms of politics, and of candidacies that challenge democracy and institutions. The emergence of political discourses that claim to defend the unprotected, marginalized and the excluded from the existing social order can be thus used as a gateway to allow the entrance or the return of authoritarian regimes and forefronts the risk of this taking a hold in the region. We should not forget that populists in Latin America, like Trump, and Mussolini before him, spoke of draining the swamp, and spoke of making the work state for "the people". Then, democracy can in fact enable populist politicians to use democratic means- one of them protests, as a vehicle for eroding democracy itself.

4. The future tensions in the region

Behind this paradox, what seems to characterize future protests in Latin America is the sharpening of political cleavages, created around identitarian divisions, and the formation of organizations (political parties or social movements), informing the emergence of political confrontations (Seiler, 2001).

The main ideological positions that we will expect to observe can be characterized as belonging to two main cleavages: 1 left vs. right wing⁴ and 2. democratic vs. authoritarian (Sanahuja and López, 2022, pp 3), these cleavages will take place in relation to the polycrisis to be faced by the region.

To understand how these cleavages will frame the way conflicts unfold across different countries in the region, we define a four-element typology that firstly discusses the political identification left/right (first political cleavage) of existing movements, and then we proceed to reflect on their relationship with the degree of democracy or autocracy (second political cleavage) and the type of tensions taking place.

Within the democrats from the left, we find progressive movements and parties in favour of expanding rights and freedoms, but in a context in which where the state takes ownership of these tasks. Thus, the tensions of economic, environmental, labour, or human rights demands would continue. In some cases, such tensions have informed the arrival of moderate leftist (or centre left) governments, such as Chile, Colombia, Mexico, or Brazil, which defend a government-led “progressive” agenda.

On the other hand, right-wing democrats, they envision the role of the state as following the ideology of the Davos Forum, and defend a classic neoliberal model, where the deepening of free trade and private enterprise are the fundamental elements to maintain an international order based on an “ideological and normative globalism” (Slobodian, 2018). Such an approach is assumed to achieve the goals of countries and societies, which are framed around average economic wellbeing, thus the defence of the wellbeing of the economy as a goal for societies.

Within democratic movements, we observe a series of demands around rights that can be heterogeneous, as in the movements that claim the defence of the traditional family vs. the rights of LGBTIQ+ citizens to have the right to be married, will lead to mobilizations with regards to sexual identities (in the cases of left leaning governments we could expect greater support for such, as opposed to right wing democratic governments who tend to be more conservative on these issues), informing the processes of construction of policies and institutions around these topics.

⁴ We would note that the distinction of left-wing and right-wing politics is more elaborate and should differentiate the understanding of political or economic right-wing vs left wing politics for an accurate characterization. In our description, when we speak about right wing or left wing, we refer to their understanding of the role of the state responding to the demands of their citizens. Then right-wing governments/movements would leave the response to societal demands as something to be dealt by markets, whereas left wing governments/movements would see this as a duty of the state.

In both cases, dissent is understood as natural, but that, faced with difficulties in the implementation and the clashes of competing visions of the state, participation and consensus remain central for the achievement of agreements between competing visions of the state and of society.

As for the non-democratic/authoritarian, we identify those on the left. These groups also defend the intervention of the State in the economy, with a strong defence of national, anti-imperialist, and anti-transnational agendas, which defend demands close to decolonial projects and with great force in territorial and racial identity demands. In this cleavage, some social movements tout their worldview as the goal to be implemented across states. Examples of this are the socio-environmental movements of Peru, Bolivia, or the Mapuche movement in Chile. It is important to note, how these protests have achieved two important things. The formation of organizational networks that, in a transnational key, have managed to create strong informational, symbolic, political, cultural, and even economic interactions that have given international strength to their demands and managed to reformulate protest to be part of a global discussion.

Right-wing non-democratic groups are closer to neo-patriotism, who defend the role of the economy as an ordering principle of societies, and the defence of the status quo, and are antagonistic to the inclusion of societal demands, or to the rights of marginalized groups. Examples of these are the actions of the current Peruvian government. This is not a feature of the past, as in Uruguay, we observe the emergence of the *Cabildo Abierto* (CA) party, led by former retired General Guido Manini Ríos - dismissed for intervening in political debates while being an active member of the Army. *Cabildo Abierto* (CA) and other parties in the region defend a punitive and securitized discourse, naturalize oppression as a mandate of the state and oppose the expansion of rights.

Current protests can be framed along these cleavages. Worryingly, it seems that non-democratic groups are on the rise or seem to be more prevalent. Questions remain on whether their style, is performative and responds to the interests of citizens for such style of politics, and once in power, democratic pathways will remain.

This panorama highlights the role of democratic movements from the right and the left. They remain central to allow and legitimize the defence of democracy as a functional form of government that is embracing of dissent and debate in a context of fragile governability, weak institutions, citizen disaffection towards political systems and the multicausal impacts of the ongoing and future economic crises.

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